

INTERNATIONAL ASTRONOMICAL UNION:

**OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY
FOR DEVELOPMENT**

**ANNUAL REPORT
2024/25**

ANNUAL REPORT 2024-25

The Office of Astronomy for Development is a joint project of the International Astronomical Union (IAU) and the South African National Research Foundation (NRF) with the support of the Department of Science, Technology, and Innovation (DSTI). The mission of the OAD is to help further the use of astronomy, including its practitioners, skills and infrastructures, as a tool for development by mobilising the human and financial resources necessary in order to realise the field's scientific, technological and cultural benefits to society.

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IMAGE CREDITS

Janik Alheit, Kyle Goetsch, SCBP
team, workshop & technical teams

MESSAGE FROM THE DIRECTOR

The past year at the OAD was truly memorable. It was a year that powerfully demonstrated what can be achieved when a dedicated group unites behind a shared goal. The OAD's vision, "Astronomy for a Better World," resonated as a guiding principle for the world's largest gathering of astronomers, the IAU General Assembly, in August 2024. It served as a pivotal moment, showcasing the OAD's remarkable organisational and leadership prowess. The event transformed a traditionally exclusive scientific assembly into one that embraced all sectors of society, prioritising accessibility, impact, and sustainability. The enduring networks and partnerships forged during this event, along with the enhanced reputation, will continue to benefit the OAD for many years to come.

The OAD team's remarkable capabilities were evident in their ability to sustain normal operations during this demanding period. This included successfully implementing the annual call for proposals, hosting a gathering of OAD regional offices in Cape Town, and advancing numerous OAD Flagship projects. We are fortunate to have a dynamic office in Cape Town, fostering close collaboration and mutual support among partners from the South African Astronomical Observatory, African Astronomical Society, Inter-university Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy, and BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network, all united by the common vision of leveraging astronomy for a better world.

The most significant challenge we faced in the past year was the reduced funding for activities. Both the IAU and the South African government have reduced their contributions due to financial constraints, impacting OAD projects and operations. However, the IAU has appointed a fundraiser to address this shortfall, and we are optimistic that these fundraising efforts will generate enough income to more than compensate for the budget reductions.

The upcoming external review of the OAD is a crucial milestone, informing its principal organisations—the IAU, NRF, and DSTI—regarding the renewal of the OAD agreement, set to conclude in 2027. This marks the third such review in the OAD's history. Our prior experiences indicate that these reviews are invaluable opportunities for stakeholder engagement and introspection. They allow us to assess the OAD's journey, acknowledge past accomplishments, and define future directions to amplify our impact in leveraging astronomy for global betterment. We eagerly anticipate involving the entire OAD community, including its family and friends, in this review process over the coming years. As Director of the OAD, I am immensely proud of our exceptional team and their extraordinary efforts during what has been a truly momentous year for the organisation.

Kevin Govender
Director, IAU Office of Astronomy for Development
June 2025

OUR ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

<https://astro4dev.org/projects-impact/>

Projects funded by the OAD through the annual call for proposals, 2013-25

HIGHLIGHTS

IMPACTFUL CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2024

The OAD played a pivotal role in organising the IAU General Assembly (GA) 2024. The OAD director and deputy director served as chair and vice-chair of the national organising committee, and together with OAD team members ensured that the first GA in Africa had a positive impact on both astronomy and society. With more than 2600 participants, including a strong presence from 28 African countries, it was the first GA to adopt an open-access approach, streaming all sessions online for free, as well as run a live radio broadcast for the entire duration of the conference. Further details about the conference can be found in the Nature Astronomy comment linked in the Publications section.

The OAD also hosted a number of meetings and events. An Institutional Meeting on Astronomy for Development featured presentations by OAD team members, projects, and regional offices on various activities and flagship projects. A networking event facilitated conversation and collaboration amongst the OAD network, including our sister organisations - Office for Astronomy Outreach (OAO), Office of Astronomy for Education (OAE), Office for

Young Astronomers (OYA), and Centre for the Protection of Dark and Quiet Sky Against Satellite Constellation Interference (CPS) - reviewers, Regional and Language Offices, project teams, and others. The event was also a celebration of the 10-year anniversary of the Southern African Regional Office (SAROAD).

The IAU Offices and Centre hosted joint sessions during the GA. The session on "Science for Society" covered topics that aligned with all the Offices and the Centre, including cultural heritage of dark skies, astronomy education for the promotion of scientific thinking, building sustainable programmes in local communities, and changing people's perceptions about our place in the Universe. A plenary session featured a keynote address by Nobel Prize winner and incoming IAU President Prof. Brian Schmidt on "*How to build an impactful career*".

Astronomy for Development at IAU GA 2024:
<https://astro4dev.org/highlights-of-the-oad-at-the-iau-ga-2024/>

*The OAD played a pivotal role in organising the IAU GA 2024 as well as contributed through several sessions and meetings
Credit: IAU GA 2024/Bradley Urion*

OAD COMMUNITY WINS BIG AT THE IAU ASTRONOMY ODE PRIZES

The OAD is pleased to share that the 2024 prize winners of the IAU Astronomy Outreach, Development and Education (ODE) Prizes are all part of the OAD community.

The Outreach Prize was awarded to our colleague from Thailand, Dr Saran Poshyachinda, who led the creation of a world-leading outreach and education programme in Thailand. His noteworthy achievement is the establishment of the National Astronomical Research Institute of Thailand (NARIT) in 2009 and the formation and expansion of the NARIT outreach team. NARIT is the host of the IAU OAD South East Asian Regional Office.

Dr Bonaventure Okere and Dr Linda Strubbe received the Education prize recognising their leadership in creating the Pan African School for Emerging Astronomers (PASEA), a high-quality educational experience in astronomy for African university

students. The PASEA school has been funded by the IAU OAD in the past, and supported directly by the IAU OAD Regional Offices in Africa.

Finally, the Development prize was awarded to the Central American Caribbean Bridge in Astrophysics (Cenca Bridge) programme, funded by the IAU OAD. Co-led by Dr Antonio Porras Valverde, Dr Gloria Fonseca Alvarez, Valeria Hurtado, and Yahira Mendoza Moncada, the project has had a transformative impact on the ability of undergraduate students in the Central America-Caribbean region to engage in astronomical research and capacity building using astronomy. Recently, the Cenca Bridge team received a 1.5 million USD grant from the Simons Foundation to continue building on the work supported by the OAD.

<https://astro4dev.org/iau-astronomy-outreach-development-and-education-ode-prizes/>

IAU Astronomy Development Prize

Antonio Porras Valverde, Gloria Fonseca Alvarez, Valeria Hurtado & Yahira Mendoza
Central American-Caribbean Bridge in Astrophysics (Cenca Bridge)

IAU Astronomy Outreach Prize

Saran Poshyachinde

IAU Astronomy Education Prize

Linda Strubbe & Bonaventure Okere
Pan-African School for Emerging Astronomers (PASEA)

OAD STAFF AND CONTRIBUTORS REWARDED FOR EXCELLENCE

*Dr. Michèle Gerbaldi awarded the Chevalière de l'Ordre National du Mérite by France
Credit: Jean Mouette /IAP-CNRS-SU*

Dr Michèle Gerbaldi, a long time friend and collaborator of the IAU and OAD received the Chevalier of the National Order of Merit (Chevalière de l'Ordre National du Mérite) by France for her contributions to astronomy. The Order of Merit rewards distinguished merit acquired either in a public, civil or military service and is awarded by the President of the French Republic. She served as deputy director and then director of the IAU International School for Young Astronomers (ISYA). Together with Professor Jean-Pierre DeGreve, she developed the Astrolab (Starlight in the University Lab) project that exposes students to the scientific method and research process through a practical activity in astronomy. The OAD has supported several Astrolab projects since 2013, building teaching capacity at universities across Africa and South America and training hundreds of students. Currently Dr Gerbaldi serves as a reviewer on the OAD evaluation committee for the call for proposals. In 2022, Dr Gerbaldi was the first laureate of the IAU "Astronomy for Development" Prize that was awarded for her leading role in the establishment of numerous international schools for young astronomers.

<https://astro4dev.org/iau-and-oad-contributor-michele-gerbaldi-awarded-by-france/>

The OAD team received awards at the Employee Recognition ceremony of the National Research Foundation's South African Astronomical Observatory (NRF|SAAO). Nuhaah Solomon was awarded in the category of "Administrative Excellence" for her exceptional organisational skills and project management, making significant contributions to the success of the IAU General Assembly 2024 through her proactive approach and professionalism. Kevin Govender received an award for "Management and Leadership Excellence" recognising his outstanding leadership at the OAD, his role in the success of the IAU General Assembly 2024, and his inclusive approach that has fostered a culture of collaboration and trust within the organisation. Duduzile Kubheka, who coordinates the societal impact work of the BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network (BITDN) collaboration, received an award in the category of "Stakeholder Service" recognising her exemplary stakeholder engagement during the IAU General Assembly and BRICS events, fostering key relationships and enhancing NRF's outreach efforts.

<https://astro4dev.org/oad-recognised-at-nrf-saao-employee-awards/>

*The OAD team at the annual awards ceremony in 2024
Credit: SAAO*

ASTRONOMY-FOR-DEVELOPMENT AT SCIENCE FORUM SOUTH AFRICA 2024

The OAD co-hosted a session with the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO) at the 2024 Science Forum South Africa. The session, titled “Astronomy for Sustainable Development: Global Impact through Indigenous Innovation”, featured a diverse panel comprising the Managing Directors of the National Research Foundation’s South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO) and SARAO, the Directors of the Department of Tourism and the OAD, and a development economist. The panel highlighted the intersections of astronomy, tourism, education, and socio-economic development.

The OAD also co-hosted a session with the African Astronomical Society (AfAS) on “Astronomy for Sustainable Development: Charting the Future of Africa”.

<https://astro4dev.org/science-forum-2024/>

ASTRONOMY’S IMPACT ON SOCIETY: SHOWCASE FROM 2024 PROJECTS

Every year, the IAU OAD provides grants and supports projects around the world that apply astronomy in the pursuit of sustainable development. In 2024, the IAU OAD funded 14 projects run by multidisciplinary teams that addressed local and global challenges through astronomy-related innovations.

Projects covered countries in Asia, Africa, South and Central America, and the Middle East. They included: astrotourism initiatives in Mongolia and the Tharparkar Desert in Pakistan; a community education programme in rural Honduras; a remote internship for marginalised students from Central America and the Caribbean; a collaboration between astronomers and artists in a Brazilian favela; projects advancing girls’ education and empowerment in Ethiopia and Kenya; teacher training workshops in Timor-Leste, among others. Presentations on the results and outcomes were shared by project teams at an online session organised by the OAD.

<https://astro4dev.org/astronomys-impact-on-society-showcase-from-2024-projects/>

PUBLICATIONS

NATURE COMMENT: IMPACT AND LEGACY OF THE IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2024

The 32nd IAU General Assembly, held for the first time on the African continent from 6–15 August 2024, marked a historic milestone in the global astronomy community. Hosted by the South African National Research Foundation through the African Astronomical Society, the conference was supported by several partners in Africa and elsewhere, including the IAU OAD.

The IAU GA National Organising Committee published two comments in Nature Astronomy: one describing the vision behind this massive endeavour, its impact and legacy, as well as the reaction from the astronomy community; and another that goes into the details of how the conference was envisioned and implemented as a fully hybrid and open-access conference.

<https://astro4dev.org/nature-comment-impact-and-legacy-of-the-xxxii-iau-general-assembly/>

NATURE COMMENT: ASTRONOMY AS A STRATEGIC DRIVER FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The IAU OAD published a comment in Nature Astronomy that highlights how astronomy, traditionally seen as a purely scientific field, is being increasingly recognised for its potential in addressing global societal needs. At first glance, astronomy might seem far removed from the pressing challenges our societies face such as poverty, inequality, education gaps, mental health issues, climate change. But astronomy has proved to be more than its science – it’s a driver of broader societal impact. From innovations such as imaging technologies and data processing tools that have led to widespread technological benefits to skills development and economic empowerment, astronomy is a versatile tool in development.

The article describes the impact of the OAD’s global work, including 236 funded projects across 112 countries that have reached over two million people and contributed to 13 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. It also outlines key thematic areas such as social development through education and inclusion, flagship initiatives promoting STEM skills and mental health, local economic growth via astrotourism, and the importance of regional offices and strategic partnerships. It concludes with a call to action for the scientific and development communities to invest in astronomy-based initiatives as a means to advance the SDGs by 2030 and beyond.

<https://rdcu.be/etI2H>

Astronomy’s tools, methods, and infrastructure have been used to tackle local and global challenges in development such as inequality, poverty, and the skills gap
Credit: IAU OAD

BEST PRACTICES ON MENTAL HEALTH INTERVENTIONS IN CONFLICT ZONES

OAD projects typically work with underserved and disadvantaged groups all across the world. This includes people living in and around conflict zones, refugee camps, and otherwise affected by conflict. We published a blog on the critical importance of mental health interventions in conflict zones, important considerations for such interventions, and best practices according to a review of literature.

<https://astro4dev.org/mental-health-interventions-in-times-of-conflict-a-summary-of-considerations-and-best-practices/>

INTEGRATING MENTAL WELL-BEING INTO ASTRONOMY AND SCIENCE ENGAGEMENT

The OAD has developed a number of resources featuring examples and providing a step-by-step guide to astronomy-based mental health interventions. The Narratives Reference Booklet is designed to empower astronomy communicators with the tools to seamlessly integrate mental health principles into their work. By aligning with Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) principles, the narratives offer a unique way to foster psychological well-being while inspiring awe and curiosity about the universe. They aim to help individuals gain perspective, find acceptance, and reconnect with their core values, all the while exploring the wonders of the cosmos.

<https://astro4dev.org/practical-look-at-combining-astronomy-and-mental-health/>

PROJECTS

IAU GRANTS SUPPORT NEW ASTRONOMY-FOR-DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS IN 2025

The IAU OAD is supporting 14 astronomy-for-development projects around the world to the tune of 100,000 Euros in 2025. The new projects target countries in Asia, Europe, South America, Africa, Australia, North America, the Caribbean, and the Middle East. They include mobile observatory STEM programmes in Malaysia and India; a multi-national collaborative radio astronomy project connecting students in China, Pakistan and Greece; personal and professional skills development projects for vulnerable children in Mexico and South Africa; a cultural astronomy experience for Aboriginal youth in Australia; astrotourism and other revenue-generating projects in Saint Lucia, Mexico and India; skills development workshops in Iran, and more.

Additionally, OAD partner, the Development in Africa with Radio Astronomy Project (DARA), is funding projects in Kenya and Botswana, through the UK's Science and Technologies Facilities Council, to stimulate the local economy through astrotourism.

List of projects funded, in alphabetical order:

- Astro-STEM Workshop, Kenya
- Australia's Cultural Night Sky: Culture, Creativity and Community at Lake Ballard, Western Australia, Australia
- Closer to the sky: co-creating astronomical knowledge in the favela complex of Cantagalo Pavão Pavãozinho (PPG) in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
- CSTERC Women Astropreneurs' Collective, India
- El Universo para ti - Astronomía para la resiliencia (The Universe for you - Astronomy for resilience), Mexico
- Elimisha Msichana Elimisha Jamii na Astronomia (Educate a Girl Educate the entire Community with Astronomy), Kenya and Uganda
- Look Up now and reconnect (LuNaR): Astrotourism for Economic, Cultural and Environmental development in Coahuila & Campeche, Mexico
- LUNAA Journeys Stargazing Training Programme, Saint Lucia
- Radio Astronomy for Development, Intercultural Innovation, and Outreach: A modern 'Silk Road' via radio astronomy education, China, Pakistan, Greece
- Reviving and Integrating Solar Energy in the Zagros region, Iran
- Rites of Passage: Connection through Astronomy, South Africa
- Scigirls Empowering girls and female teachers through astronomy in rural areas affected by conflict, Ethiopia
- Sparking STEM Interest through Mobile Observatory in Malaysia
- Starlight Pathways: Bringing Astronomy to Every Child, India
- Anga Explorers for Development, Kenya (funded by DARA)
- AstroGuides: Transforming Tours with Astrotourism, Botswana (funded by DARA)

The OAD has also compiled a list of recommended proposals that were approved by the reviewers but could not be funded. You can browse through the Recommended list and contact us for more details or to support one or more projects. The OAD welcomes funding partners who could support those projects that we are unable to fund.

<https://astro4dev.org/iau-grants-to-support-13-new-astronomy-for-development-projects-in-2025/>

Influencing Attitudes

VALUE RE-ORIENTATION AMONG INMATES THROUGH ASTRONOMY

Astro-prison is an astronomy-based programme that reached 375 inmates in correctional centres in Nigeria. By leveraging the awe and global perspective offered by astronomy, the project sought to influence and re-orient values of the prisoners. It also boosted the morale of all inmates and prepared them for a more responsible life after their incarceration through strategic skills transfer.

<https://astro4dev.org/value-re-orientation-among-inmates-through-astronomy/>

Influencing Attitudes

ASTRO BOARDGAMES SPARK INTEREST IN SCIENCE IN GUATEMALA

The Inclusive Astronomy project in Guatemala carried out interactive activities aimed at promoting science through astronomy in low-income rural towns with significant First Nation populations
Credit: IAU OAD/ Inclusive Astronomy in Guatemala

The Inclusive Astronomy in Guatemala project promoted science amongst children, notably in lower-income rural areas with substantial First Nation communities, through astronomy activities. The project delivered interactive and entertaining workshops, and developed educational games, including: a galactic astronomy dice game, two memory games focused on astronomy and general science, a cosmic checkers game, and a cosmic quiz. Materials were developed in Spanish, K'iche' and Q'eqchi'. These activities and games led to an increased interest in science among children, and increased relevance of science to First Nation communities.

<https://astro4dev.org/fancy-a-game-of-cosmic-checkers-astro-boardgames-spark-interest-in-science-in-guatemala/>

WORKSHOP FOR DEVELOPING SCIENCE EDUCATION IN TIMOR-LESTE

The Timor-Leste National Commission for UNESCO (TLNCU) and its science division, SESIM, organised a training workshop for physics teachers at the high school level. The workshop increased the teachers' knowledge in astronomy and improved their confidence in teaching science. Teachers were provided teaching materials and activities and connected with the Knua Prátika in their municipality. The team will also organise training at other Knua Prátika (laboratories) and a one day science exposition for students.

<https://astro4dev.org/workshop-for-developing-astronomy-education-in-timor-leste/>

Skills Development

Skills Development

PAN-AFRICAN ASTRONOMY SCHOOL INFLUENCES CAREER CHOICE OF STUDENTS

PASEA trains the next generation of African scientists and innovators, credits: IAU OAD/PASEA

The Pan-African School for Emerging Astronomers (PASEA) 2024, which won the IAU Education ODE prize, was the sixth in a series of schools that aim to strengthen students' scientific thinking and build local scientific communities in Africa. It combined interactive lectures, problem-solving sessions, hands-on experience and inquiry-based activities to train the next generation of African scientists and innovators. Surveys conducted before and after the school showed that it was very influential for the intending choice of career/study of over 80% of the participants.

<https://astro4dev.org/pan-african-astronomy-school-influences-career-choice-of-students/>

Employment

Gender Equity

WOMEN ASTROPRENEURS COLLECTIVE SUPPORTS FIRST-GENERATION FEMALE GRADUATES IN THE WORKFORCE

The CWAPC Women Astropreneurs Collective project in India aims to integrate first-generation female graduates into the workforce by equipping them with skills needed to produce astronomy products, and foster entrepreneurship among women. Ultimately, the project aims to empower women to excel in traditionally male-dominated technical fields. The project successfully completed the orientation programme for their trainees which included a pre-competency survey with participants. The initial phase of telescope construction workshops and industry visits were completed. Additionally, the team organised a special session on HAM Radio and Satellite Communications.

<https://astro4dev.org/first-phase-of-women-astropreneurs-collective-underway-in-india/>

Gender Equity

ADDRESSING SCHOOL DROPOUTS AMONG GIRLS IN RURAL KENYA AND UGANDA

The EMEJA project aims to address the issue of high dropout rates among girls in rural Kenya and Uganda. Through multiple complementary interventions such as mentorship and education outreach, STEM workshops, teacher training, digital literacy training, and tuition scholarships, the project has impacted over 40,000 schoolgirls and parents across 40 primary and 14 secondary schools in Kenya and Uganda. The results are promising - more girls are now attending school regularly, an increased number of girls are enrolling in secondary education, reduced cases of teen pregnancies, better academic performance and higher enrolment in Physics, and increased interest in STEM careers among girls.

<https://astro4dev.org/better-grades-higher-enrolment-changed-attitudes-to-stem-emejas-impact-in-rural-kenya/>

Inclusion

CULTURALLY RELEVANT EDUCATIONAL CONTENT FOR KIDS

Kainaat Kids produces high quality astronomy videos for kids in Urdu and Hindi centered on curiosity-driven questions such as, Why is the sky blue, or Where do comets come from? These videos use a combination of live hosts (one from Pakistan and one from India) and original animations that root the content in a local cultural context. The team has published 10 videos in this latest series funded by the OAD, with more than 90 videos overall covering astronomy news and events.

<https://astro4dev.org/culturally-relevant-astronomy-videos-for-kids-in-pakistan/>

Educational activities were conducted for school students in Pakistan
Credits: IAU OAD/Astronomy Videos for Kids in Schools, Pakistan

Inclusion

LIGHTSOUND DEVICES OPEN UP ASTRONOMY TO BVI AUDIENCES

LightSound, a device designed for blind or low-vision individuals to experience eclipses through sound, uses a light sensor to convert light intensity into audible signals. The LightSound team conducted workshops enabling participants to build more than 100 devices, which were then donated to various groups organising eclipse events, impacting hundreds of thousands of people across the United States, Mexico, and Canada. The team also partnered with the American Council for the Blind to host a live stream event during the 2024 total solar eclipse reaching several thousand people.

<https://astro4dev.org/lightsound-devices-open-up-astronomy-to-bvi-audiences/>

Inclusion

DECOLONISING SCHOOL EDUCATION IN BRAZIL THROUGH ASTRONOMY

To address the under-representation of women, black, LGBTQIA+ and Indigenous people in science in Brazil, the OruMbya project developed reading circles, workshops on the stories of the heavens, and a library with books that bring out the voices of these people. Targeting elementary and high school students and teachers in public schools, the project organised reading circles, classroom astronomy activities, and conversations with astronomers. The project exposed students to books dealing with black and Indigenous issues through the interesting lens of astronomy, and encouraged reading and writing. Teachers reported a positive impact on their teaching practice.

<https://astro4dev.org/decolonising-school-education-in-brazil-through-astronomy/>

The OruMbya project used astronomy and literature to strengthen primary and secondary education in science, targeting children and young people living in extreme social vulnerability in Brazil.
Credit: IAU OAD/ OruMbya - a library of silenced voices

FLAGSHIPS

FLAGSHIP 1: ASTROTOURISM

The Astrotourism flagship harnesses the potent synergy of astronomy and tourism to catalyse socioeconomic development through employment and job creation, skills training, and education. Recognising the inherent dark skies and rich natural and cultural heritage in many rural areas, this flagship initiative is dedicated to democratising the benefits of astronomy-based tourism. By doing so, we aspire to empower communities, ensuring that the transformative potential of astrotourism becomes an inclusive force, fostering economic growth while preserving local identities.

DEDICATED WEBSITE ON ASTROTOURISM

The OAD launched a dedicated website that aims to promote astrotourism as a means to drive economic development. The platform provides information on some of the astrotourism initiatives globally, including those funded by the OAD through its grants programme. It also hosts resources developed by the OAD to catalyse the creation of new astrotourism businesses. We will continue to publish resources and data on the state of astrotourism around the world. Soon, we will create an astrotourism community of practice, a peer supported learning space for people running astrotourism initiatives or planning to do so. To join the community or know more, please contact us at astrotourism@astro4dev.org.

<https://astrotourism.astro4dev.org/>

ASTROTOURISM PROJECT IN MALAYSIA MAKES A MARK

The OAD funded an astrotourism project in Langkawi, Malaysia that revamped the tourism sector in the region by establishing a new niche in astronomy tourism. The project trained tour guides on astronomy and the night sky, observation, photography, cultural heritage, and entrepreneurship skills. It also engaged tourism stakeholders which resulted in three city councils adopting astrotourism, and attention from Tourism Malaysia. Further, four tour companies and three 5-star resorts started offering stargazing and custom astrotourism packages, five observatories partnered with astroguides, and two tourism institutes introduced astronomy education and tourism in their tourism certificate. The project has secured additional grants for further activities.

<https://astro4dev.org/astro-tourism-project-in-malaysia-makes-a-mark/>

*The Guide Star project revamped the tourism sector in Langkawi, Malaysia by establishing a new niche in astronomy tourism
Credit: IAU OAD/ Langkawians Guide Malaysians to the Stars*

NATIONAL ASTROTOURISM STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP IN SOUTH AFRICA

Members of the OAD team participated in the National Astrotourism Broader Stakeholder Workshop in early 2025 in Carnarvon, South Africa. Hosted by the South African Departments of Tourism, and Science, Technology and Innovation (DSTI), the workshop focused on the implementation of South Africa's Astrotourism Strategy. The two-day event brought together stakeholders from across astronomy, tourism, and science to explore the potential of astrotourism for sustainable development and community engagement.

Dr Joyful Mdhuli presented on 'Community-led Astrotourism Initiatives', highlighting the role of local communities in driving sustainable astrotourism, while Kevin Govender facilitated discussions on Inclusive Tourism Growth & Partnerships, emphasising collaboration and sustainable growth in the sector.

<https://astro4dev.org/oad-attends-national-astro-tourism-stakeholder-workshop-in-south-africa/>

TELL US ABOUT YOUR ASTROTOURISM INITIATIVE

To advance astrotourism, the OAD seeks to understand initiatives around the globe and their varying approaches. We have launched an open survey to learn about the objectives and obstacles of astronomy tourism operators and businesses. Those involved in astrotourism are encouraged to participate by completing the survey. Preliminary survey findings can be found on our website.

<https://astro4dev.org/astrotourism-initiatives-survey/>

FLAGSHIP 2: ASTRONOMY FOR MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

The Astronomy for Mental Health flagship aims to improve people's mental health and well-being by harnessing the rejuvenating characteristics of nature-based activities such as stargazing. The concept is centred on using astronomy to foster a profound sense of awe in order to create a context or setting for self-exploration and reflection. The overarching goal is to use astronomy to empower individuals and communities to reach their full potential. The project utilises diverse methods within the realm of astronomy, such as stargazing and educational initiatives, and partnerships within the mental health and psychology communities, to address mental health challenges effectively.

EXPLORING YOUR CONNECTION TO THE NATURAL WORLD AT NIGHT

The OAD is collaborating with the University of Derby on a research project exploring how people across the globe connect with the night. This work is part of our Astronomy for Mental Health flagship that is focused on harnessing the inspirational potential of astronomy, and using it as a tool for improving people's mental health and well-being. We would like to understand how people from across the world experience the night – its biodiversity, landscapes, as well as the night sky. We encourage you to complete a brief survey to support this study.

<https://astro4dev.org/exploring-peoples-connection-to-the-natural-world-at-night/>

INTRODUCING GUIDED MEDITATION WITH AN ASTRONOMICAL TWIST

The OAD has developed a series of guided meditation sessions, created in partnership with astrophysicist and renowned mindfulness practitioner, Dr Mark Westmoquette. This unique collection of six sessions is available for free online, offering a harmonious blend of relaxation techniques and astronomy education.

Research has shown that meditation can significantly improve mental health by reducing stress, enhancing emotional well-being, and promoting cognitive function. Combining it with astronomy creates an appealing experience for a diverse audience, enhancing both mental health and astronomical knowledge. These sessions, thus, offer a novel way for individuals to unwind and relax.

<https://astro4dev.org/introducing-guided-meditation-with-an-astronomical-twist-a-collaboration-between-the-oad-and-mark-westmoquette/>

FLAGSHIP 3: HACKATHONS FOR DEVELOPMENT

The mission of Hackathons for Development (Hack4dev) is to build a more resilient world, one that advances both skills development and innovation. By running hackathons across the globe, we help individuals and communities develop the agility needed to respond to disruptive change. Hack4dev is an open collaboration between the OAD and various partners, including Development in Africa with Radio Astronomy, the Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy, African Astronomical Society, BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network, and others.

SKA DATA CHALLENGE: TRAINING THE NEXT GENERATION OF AFRICAN SCIENTISTS

To support the global astronomy community in preparing for the massive data volumes expected from the Square Kilometre Array (SKA), the SKA Observatory has launched a series of data challenges. The challenges aim to build community expertise in calibration, data processing, and scientific analysis and are open to scientists across the world.

Recognising the value of these challenges in developing essential skills for postgraduate astronomers, Hack4dev adapted an SKA Data Challenge into a hackathon. The challenge was redesigned with associated Jupyter notebooks, guiding participants through key steps of astronomical data processing, from source finding and characterisation to source classification. It was successfully run at the African Astronomical Society (AfAS) 2025 Data Science Hackathon, marking a significant milestone in preparing African postgraduate astronomers to tackle the data challenges of the SKA.

<https://astro4dev.org/ska-data-challenge-training-the-next-generation-of-african-scientists/>

IAU OAD AND PARTNERS SUPPORTED 13 HACKATHONS GLOBALLY IN 2025

Hack4dev hosted 13 data science hackathons across 12 countries between February and April 2025. Hackathons took place in Botswana, Brazil, Chile, Ethiopia, Ghana, India, Kenya, Madagascar, Mozambique, Namibia, Rwanda, and South Africa. The events offered participants the opportunity to tackle data challenges using cutting-edge techniques and infrastructure; develop a machine learning pipeline for CubeSats; collaborate with peers; and compete against regional teams from around the globe. Preliminary analysis of the solutions developed by the teams indicate that the hackathons succeeded in significantly improving the known solutions.

<https://astro4dev.org/iau-oad-and-partners-to-support-13-hackathons-globally-in-2025-under-the-hack4dev-collaboration/>

Participants at a trainers programme for hackathon organisers at Wits University in Johannesburg, South Africa
Credit: Hack4dev

MEETINGS AND EVENTS

COMMUNICATING ASTRONOMY WITH THE PUBLIC CONFERENCE

The OAD team participated in the 2024 Communicating Astronomy with the Public Conference (CAP2024), organised by the IAU. The team presented a talk, a workshop, and two posters.

A joint presentation by Dr Mdhuli and Samyukta Manikumar, titled “Leveraging Astrotourism for Sustainable Development and Public Astronomy Outreach”, explored the intersection of tourism and astronomy as a means of fostering sustainable development. A workshop on “Integrating Astronomy for Mental Well-being”, led by Dr Mdhuli, offered an interactive session on using astronomy outreach as a tool to support mental health.

Additionally, two poster presentations were featured and presented by Dominic Vertue: “The Preliminary Journey into Astronomy’s Impact on Mental Well-being” and “Art and Astronomy: Bridging the Cosmos through Creative Expression.”

<https://astro4dev.org/oad-at-communicating-astronomy-with-the-public-conference-cap2024/>

SAASTEC CONFERENCE

Dominic Vertue of the OAD led an “Astronomy in Mental Health” workshop at the 2024 Southern African Association of Science and Technology Centres (SAASTEC) conference. This session, a joint effort by the OAD and the Office for Astronomy Outreach (OAO), aimed to equip participants with the skills to lead an astronomy-themed activity that incorporated principles of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). The objective was to foster a learning environment that also promoted self-reflection and emotional development.

The activity utilised the expansive universe as a metaphor for human experiences, merging the wonder of astronomical exploration with prompts for introspection. Reflective narratives were woven into the activity. For example: similar to the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB), we carry past experiences that continue to influence us. However, with time, our perception of these moments often shifts, becoming less intense and more manageable. Just as this ancient light has transformed, we too can reframe past experiences, understanding their impact without being overwhelmed by them.

The session attracted staff and directors from various science centres who provided valuable insights into how such activities could be adapted and integrated into science outreach initiatives.

<https://astro4dev.org/astronomy-in-mental-health-workshop-at-saastec-2024/>

AMERICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY MEETING

OAD Director, Kevin Govender, and Deputy Director, Dr Charles Takalana attended the American Astronomical Society (AAS) meeting in the US in January 2025, one of the largest astronomy gatherings globally. They presented the outcomes of the IAU General Assembly and the OAD’s work to the AAS Strategic Assembly, shared exhibition space with the IAU OAD North American Regional Office, and met key individuals.

AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY CONFERENCE

At the African Astronomical Society Conference in March 2025, the OAD organised a special session focused on Astronomy for Development in Africa. This session underscored the influence of OAD-supported initiatives across the continent and presented our flagship projects along with perspectives from our regional offices. OAD Fellows Samyukta Manikumar and Dominic Vertue presented on “The Potential of Astrotourism in Africa” and “Astronomy, Mental Health, and Outreach,” respectively.

<https://astro4dev.org/astro4dev-at-the-afas-2025-conference/>

FULL MOON MASHUPS SERIES

OAD Full Moon Mashups foster interdisciplinary connections, brainstorming, and impactful partnerships. Each session includes a brief presentation on a development topic, followed by facilitated discussions to encourage exchange and collaboration.

The series started as monthly discussions in February 2025. Recent gatherings have covered:

- **Dark Skies:** With Anna Levin, author of “Dark Skies”, the session explored the significance of darkness in various cultures, its role in maintaining ecological balance, and impact on human well-being. The conversation also highlighted the need to reframe our relationship with darkness, recognising its value and appreciating its benefits. The OAD advocates for dark sky conservation through our flagship projects on astrotourism and astronomy for mental health.

<https://astro4dev.org/a-conversation-on-dark-skies-with-author-anna-levin/>

- **Impact of Mega Astronomy Infrastructure on Rural Communities:** Dr Daniel Mokhohlane shared his research on the societal impact of mega astronomy infrastructures - specifically the Southern African Large Telescope (SALT) and the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) - on rural communities in South Africa. The presentation emphasised the need for community involvement, transparency, and collaborative frameworks to ensure that such projects contribute meaningfully to local development.

<https://astro4dev.org/full-moon-mashup-recap-exploring-the-impact-of-mega-astronomy-infrastructure-on-rural-communities/>

Join one of our upcoming sessions online:
<https://astro4dev.org/full-moon-mashups/>

REGIONAL OFFICES

REGIONAL OFFICES

Regional Office

Host Country

Andean ROAD

Colombia and Peru

Arab World ROAD and Arabic Language LOAD

Jordan

East African ROAD

Ethiopia

East Asian ROAD and Chinese Language LOAD

China

European ROAD

Netherlands

North American ROAD

United States

Portuguese LOAD

Portugal

South East Asian ROAD

Thailand

South West and Central Asian ROAD

Armenia

Southern African ROAD

Zambia

West African ROAD

Nigeria

*ROAD - Regional Office of Astronomy for Development

*LOAD - Language Office of Astronomy for Development

Andean

- The office supports an initiative to establish a Dark Sky Law in Colombia to regulate light pollution.
- In September 2024, the Andean ROAD supported the organisation of the first astronomical camp at the Silatupue Astronomical and Cultural Observatory to support astrotourism in the Indigenous communities of southern Colombia.

Arab World and Arabic Language

- Arab World (AW) ROAD, in collaboration with the Arab Union of Astronomy and Space Sciences, led numerous educational and public outreach activities across Arab countries, emphasising inclusive astronomy communication, gender equality, and dark skies awareness.
- AW-ROAD and its Arabic Language Expertise Center (AW-LOAD) strengthened Arabic-language science communication, offering specialised programmes and capacity-building initiatives for educators, students, and amateur astronomers.

East Africa

- A Transient Array Radio Telescope (TART) installation and training workshop was held in August 2024 at the Technical University of Kenya. The event was hosted by the Kenya Space Agency in collaboration with the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO).
- The second edition of SciGirls: Empowering Girls and Female Teachers in Science Through Astronomy, an OAD-funded project, was conducted in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Three Regional Data Science Hackathons were conducted in Ethiopia and Kenya as part of the 2025 Hackathons for Development (Hack4Dev) initiative, from February to March 2025.

East Asia and Chinese Language

- All the observatories of the Chinese Academy of Sciences held their Public Science Day and Shanghai Science Festival, inviting the public

- into laboratories and research centres to experience the beauty of science and how it changes our lives.
- The China Astronomical Society's College Student Astronomy Innovation Works Collection event was successfully organised. It included popular science, science education resources, topics such as astrotourism and the relationship between astronomy and psychology.

Europe

- The European Regional Office organised a high-level coordination meeting in Leiden for representatives of all major Ukrainian astronomical institutions and Dutch/European partners, focused on developing a long-term recovery plan for Ukrainian astronomy. <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/news/2025/06/working-together-to-rebuild-ukrainian-astronomy>
- The Erasmus+ International Credit Mobility scheme between Leiden and partner countries — Armenia, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Colombia, and Ukraine — was launched, with several mobilities already completed and others currently ongoing.

North America

- The second cohort of the Women's and Girls in Astronomy Program (WGAP) developed projects across the North American region that used astronomy as a tool to help local communities. <https://naroad.astro4dev.org/na-road-projects/women-and-girls-astronomy-program/>
- North America ROAD in collaboration with the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach, IAU Office of Astronomy for Education and the Astrofísicos en Acción lead a series of events to celebrate the "World Science Day for Peace and Development" in Mexico. <https://naroad.astro4dev.org/na-road-projects/world-science-day/>

Portuguese Language

- As part of the Lusophone Constellation Project, the Portuguese Language Office of Astronomy for Development (PLOAD) celebrated the following: International Day for Women and Girls in Science on 11 February, Portuguese Language Day on 5 May and World Science Day for Peace and Development on 10 November.
- PLOAD co-organised a Portuguese session at the Shaw-IAU Workshop on Astronomy for Education, dedicated to Pathways to Development and Peace in alignment with the celebration of World Science Day for Peace and Development. <https://astro4edu.org/shaw-iau/sessions/portuguese-language-community-meeting-2024-workshop/>
- PLOAD ran a training session for the Luanda Science Centre in Angola on using Astronomy and Planetarium Software.

South East Asia

- Southeast Asia Planetarium, Education and Outreach conference (SEA-PEO2024) was hosted in November 2024. <https://indico.narit.or.th/event/207/>
- The Regional Office organised a star party at a designated dark sky site to promote as astrotourism. Over two thousand participants showed up and several volunteers and amateur astronomers were involved. Another dark sky awareness campaign in Bangkok was attended by 35,000 people.
- SEA ROAD was involved in the ASEAN Astronomy Camp, an entry-level youth astronomy camp for 15-19 years old students enrolling in secondary school. It was very successful with overwhelmingly positive feedback from students who formed strong bonds with each other.

South West and Central Asia

- The South West and Central Asia Regional Office (SWCA ROAD) organised the Armenian Astronomical Society 25th anniversary meeting "Relation of Astronomy to other Sciences, Culture and Society". https://www.bao.am/meetings/meetings/RASCS/index_eng.html
- Two Astronomy Teachers Training Workshops in 2024 were organised in collaboration with the IAU Office of Astronomy for Education, Network for Astronomy School Education (NASE) and Galileo Teachers Training Programme (GTTP).
- The 9th Byurakan International Summer School and the 4th Regional Astronomical Workshop (4RAW) were organised in September 2024.

Southern Africa

- The Southern African Regional Office (SA ROAD) celebrated its 10th Anniversary during the IAU General Assembly 2024.
- SA ROAD is hosting an Astrolab workshop in August 2025 at Sol Plaatje University in South Africa, supported by the OAD. <https://astro4dev.org/astrolab-starlight-in-the-university-lab/>

West Africa

- The West African Regional Office, in partnership with Okany Chioma, delivered astronomy hands-on activities such as solar system modelling and the construction of optical telescopes to 40 female students.
- The office hosted a women and girls in astronomy event in March 2025 which included interactive sessions with female scientists and engineers and a planetarium show.

PARTNERSHIPS

AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (AFAS)

The African Astronomical Society, established in 2011, is a pan-African professional society of astronomers that strives to play an essential role in the development of astronomy across the continent. AfAS promotes research collaborations, encourages the study and application of astronomy, supports the amateur astronomy community, and advises stakeholders on astronomy-related policies. Through its activities, AfAS ensures that Africa sustains a stable and vibrant astronomical environment capable of contributing to knowledge-based economies. The Society has over 400 members from across Africa and the diaspora, comprising researchers, educators, and outreach practitioners.

The partnership between AfAS and the OAD reflects a shared vision to leverage astronomy in support of sustainable development across Africa. We work closely to implement joint initiatives, communication and public engagement activities, and strategic support for institutional development. Both organisations played key roles in organising the first-ever IAU General Assembly on African soil in 2024, ensuring broad participation and a lasting legacy. The AfAS - OAD partnership continues to work towards building an inclusive, coordinated, and impactful astronomy ecosystem that contributes meaningfully to both the scientific enterprise and the broader goals of societal transformation.

DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA WITH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA)

DARA is a joint UK-South African development project funded by the United Kingdom's International Science Partnership Fund through the Science and Technology Facilities Council. It aims to build high-tech skills using radio astronomy in several African partner countries, including Ghana, Kenya, Botswana, Namibia, Zambia, Madagascar, Mozambique, and Mauritius. DARA grew out of the understanding that radio astronomy brings together the full range of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) skills that are critical to building strong, knowledge-based economies.

The partnership with the IAU-OAD reflects a shared commitment to the astronomy-for-development vision. As part of this collaboration, the OAD engages with DARA student cohorts, guiding them in designing astronomy-based projects aimed at addressing challenges within their own communities and contexts. DARA also funds some of these projects to support their implementation.

INTER-UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE FOR DATA INTENSIVE ASTRONOMY (IDIA)

The Inter-University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy (IDIA) is a collaborative initiative between the Universities of Cape Town, the Western Cape, and Pretoria, aimed at building South Africa's capacity in data-intensive research, particularly in the era of astronomy infrastructure such as MeerKAT and the Square Kilometre Array (SKA). By offering a powerful cloud-based research platform, IDIA enables scientists to engage in cutting-edge astronomy, data visualisation, machine learning, and collaborative research. In partnership with the OAD and others, IDIA contributes to the Hack4dev project, an innovative initiative that uses hackathons to apply astronomical data science tools to real-world development challenges. Through this collaboration, IDIA provides both computational resources and expert support, advancing the OAD's mission of leveraging astronomy for sustainable development while empowering early-career researchers to work at the intersection of data science and societal impact.

BRICS INTELLIGENT TELESCOPE AND DATA NETWORK (BITDN)

BRICS, comprising Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa, and new members such as Egypt, Ethiopia, Iran, the United Arab Emirates, and Indonesia, reflect a growing commitment among emerging economies to collaborate on global challenges. In the field of astronomy, the BRICS Astronomy Working Group serves as a platform to advance joint scientific initiatives, build human capital, and strengthen public engagement. One of its key projects, the BRICS Intelligent Telescope and Data Network (BITDN), connects researchers and infrastructure across member states to drive innovation in data-intensive astronomy.

The OAD works closely with BITDN on the societal impact of astronomy by hosting, as part of the OAD team, the BITDN Project Coordinator Duduzile Kubheka. Activities include hackathons, community initiatives, and workshops. As BRICS grows, these collaborations present an opportunity to engage new member countries and deepen the impact of astronomy as a driver for skills development, technological development, and sustainable growth.

PEOPLE

CURRENT TEAM

Kevin Govender:
Director

Charles Takalana:
Deputy Director

Ramasamy Venugopal:
Operations & Programs

Danielle Naidoo:
Intern

Moleboge Lekoloane:
Intern

Duduzile Kubheka:
BITDN Project Coordinator

Joyful Mdhuli:
Flagships Coordinator

Dominic Vertue:
OAD Fellow

Nuhaah Solomon:
Admin & Logistics

Azasiwe Mancwatela:
Intern

PAST CONTRIBUTORS

Mduduzi Ndebele:
Intern

Genevieve Marshall:
OAD Fellow

Andrea Girolamodibari:
Intern

Samyukta Manikumar:
OAD Fellow

FINANCE

FINANCE

COMPLIANCE

The OAD operates within the financial systems and policies of the NRF, which comply with South African national legislation. These figures are extracted directly from the financial reports within the SAAO/NRF system. Compliance of the OAD's financial transactions to the relevant policies is tested through annual audits of the SAAO and NRF. The OAD financial year (April to March) is different as compared to the implementation of funded projects (calendar year), and long-term special projects or grants (which can be multi-year).

OPERATIONS

For the duration of the IAU-NRF agreement, the OAD receives an annual core income from the DSTI/NRF and the IAU, all administered through the NRF. Since the renewed IAU-NRF agreement in 2022, the DSTI/NRF provides an annual contribution towards OAD operations with inflationary increases each year. The IAU provides a fixed amount of €70,000 per year and invests in fundraising activities that ultimately benefit the OAD. In addition, the IAU funds the annual call for proposals (initially €120,000 per year but reducing to €100,000 for 2025 projects; €80,000 for 2026 projects and €60,000 for 2027 projects). Since 2016, these project grants have been paid directly from the IAU headquarters in Paris. The total allocation for 2025 projects was €100,500.

INCOME

For the 2024-2025 financial year, the DSTI/NRF provided R4,215,613 and the IAU provided R1,367,997 (total core income of R5,583,610). There were also carryover funds of R1,405,687 which was previously reserved for multi-year projects. We anticipate that fundraising efforts will result in greater income in the new financial year.

EXPENDITURE

The 2024-2025 financial year had large costs associated with subsistence and travel, especially related to the IAU General Assembly, where the OAD played a key role and hosted several international visitors including its 11 regional offices. The largest expenses for the financial year remain staff expenses including salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment and training (R3,648,027) and special project funding for flagships and related activities (R1,769,707). There was a very slight overspend (0.89%) in terms of income vs expenditure, but this will be easily absorbed in the new financial year.

Item	2024/25 Actual- in kZAR
Income	8899
IAU Contributions	1368
DSTI Contributions	4216
Carryover funds	1406
IAU Project funding	1909
Expenditure	8979
Staff expenses (salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment, training)	3658
Office expenses (infrastructure and running costs)	290
Subsistence and Travel	1082
Workshops and conferences	177
Production, printing and distribution of materials	93
OAD Special Projects (Flagships and postdoc grants)	1770
IAU Project Grants (€100,500)	1909
Income - Expenditure	-80

INCOME

EXPENDITURE

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